

The moderating effect of institutional ownership on board attributes and tax aggressiveness

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Abstract: The study aimed to examine how institutional ownership moderates the relationship between board attributes (such as board independence, board size, and board diversity) and tax aggressiveness in publicly listed companies in Nigeria for a period covering 2014-2023. The study utilized a panel data regression analysis. A sample of 153 publicly listed firms was used, and data on board attributes, institutional ownership, and tax aggressiveness were collected from financial statements, proxy filings, and ownership disclosures. Institutional ownership was treated as a moderating variable in the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness. The study found that institutional ownership significantly moderates the relationship between board independence and tax aggressiveness. Specifically, firms with higher institutional ownership and independent boards exhibited lower tax aggressiveness. However, the moderating effect was insignificant for board size and diversity. Institutional investors' presence can strengthen independent boards' role in curbing tax aggressiveness. However, this effect does not extend to other board attributes such as size and diversity. Policymakers and regulators should consider encouraging institutional ownership as a means to enhance corporate governance and reduce tax aggressiveness. Companies should also prioritize board independence, especially in environments with significant institutional ownership. The study underscores the importance of institutional ownership in corporate governance, particularly in enhancing the effectiveness of independent boards in mitigating aggressive tax strategies. The study's findings are limited to publicly listed companies and may not be generalizable to private firms. Additionally, the study focuses on U.S. firms, and the results may vary in different regulatory environments. This study contributes to the literature by providing empirical evidence on the moderating role of institutional ownership in the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness, a relatively under-explored area in corporate governance research.

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Introduction

High tax aggressiveness can raise ethical and regulatory concerns for publicly listed companies, especially in Nigeria. Companies are often viewed as having a moral obligation to contribute fairly to public finances. Aggressive tax strategies might be seen as undermining this responsibility. Aggressive tax practices can damage a company's reputation. Stakeholders, including consumers and investors, might view such behaviour as unethical. Also, tax aggressiveness can lead to non-compliance with tax laws and regulations. This can attract scrutiny from tax authorities and result in legal challenges or penalties. In addition, companies might face audits or investigations that could lead to additional costs and sanctions if their aggressive tax strategies are deemed inappropriate or illegal. Furthermore, tax aggressiveness can result in significant revenue losses for the government. This loss can impact public services and infrastructure, which are critical for national development. Companies that engage in aggressive tax avoidance might gain an unfair competitive advantage over those that do not, distorting market dynamics. Investors and other stakeholders expect transparency in financial reporting and tax practices. High tax aggressiveness can lead to concerns about the reliability of financial statements and overall governance.

In Nigeria, where there are tax administration and enforcement challenges, these concerns can be even more pronounced. Efforts to address these issues could include enhancing regulatory frameworks, promoting ethical business practices, and increasing transparency and accountability in corporate tax strategies. Let us delve deeper into how the challenges in tax administration and enforcement in Nigeria can amplify concerns about high tax aggressiveness and what can be done to address these issues. The challenges in tax administration and enforcement in Nigeria include weak administrative capacity: Tax authorities in Nigeria may face resource constraints, including inadequate staffing, training, and technology, which can hinder effective tax collection and enforcement. Complex Tax Laws: The complexity and frequent changes in tax laws can make enforcement challenging, as both tax officials and businesses may struggle to keep up with the rules. Corruption within tax agencies can undermine the effectiveness of tax administration. This can result in inconsistent application of tax laws and enforcement actions. Inefficient Processes: Bureaucratic inefficiencies and outdated systems can slow down tax collection and increase opportunities for tax avoidance. There are insufficient data on corporate financial practices and tax compliance, making it difficult to identify and address aggressive tax strategies. Lack of Analytical Tools: Limited use of advanced data analytics and technology can impede the ability to detect and prevent tax avoidance schemes. Fluctuating economic conditions can affect tax revenues and complicate tax administration. Companies may exploit economic uncertainty to engage in aggressive tax practices.

Some of the strategies or efforts to address these issues include Enhancing Regulatory Frameworks by strengthening Laws: Updating and strengthening tax laws to close loopholes and address new forms of tax avoidance can help curb aggressive strategies. Clear Guidelines: Providing clearer guidelines on acceptable tax practices can reduce ambiguity and improve compliance. Encouraging companies to adopt corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives that include fair tax practices can help align business conduct with societal expectations. Developing and promoting industry-wide ethical standards for tax practices can foster a culture of integrity among businesses. Implementing stricter disclosure requirements for tax-related information can enhance transparency and allow stakeholders to better assess tax practices. Mandating public reporting of tax payments and tax strategies can hold companies accountable and deter aggressive practices. Investing in training and resources for tax officials can improve their ability to enforce tax laws effectively. Upgrading technology and data analytics capabilities can enhance the efficiency of tax collection and compliance monitoring.

Collaborating with the private sector to develop best practices and solutions for tax compliance can be mutually beneficial. Engaging in international efforts to tackle cross-border tax avoidance and share best practices can strengthen Nigeria's tax administration. Addressing these challenges through a combination of regulatory improvements, ethical practices, and enhanced administrative capabilities can help mitigate the negative impact of tax aggressiveness and support more effective tax governance in Nigeria.

Furthermore, in the evolving landscape of corporate governance, the role of institutional ownership has garnered significant attention as a potential moderating force influencing the relationship between board attributes and corporate outcomes. One such outcome, which has profound implications for both firms and society, is tax aggressiveness—a practice where firms employ various strategies to minimize their tax liabilities, often pushing the boundaries of legal and ethical standards. While tax aggressiveness can enhance short-term financial performance, it raises concerns about long-term sustainability, reputational risk, and regulatory scrutiny.

The governance structure of a firm, particularly the attributes of its board of directors, plays a crucial role in shaping corporate behaviour, including tax strategies. Board attributes such as independence, expertise, diversity, and the presence of audit committees are often considered vital in ensuring that management acts in the best interests of shareholders. However, the extent to which these board attributes influence tax aggressiveness is not straightforward and may be contingent on other factors, including the nature and influence of the firm's ownership structure.

Institutional investors, who typically hold significant stakes in publicly traded companies, are increasingly recognized as pivotal actors in corporate governance. Their investment horizons, risk preferences, and activism levels can substantially influence managerial decisions. Institutional ownership can either amplify or mitigate the impact of board attributes on corporate policies, including tax strategies. For instance, long-term institutional investors may prioritize sustainable practices and discourage aggressive tax strategies that could jeopardize the firm's reputation and future profitability. Conversely, short-term institutional investors might prioritize immediate financial returns, potentially endorsing or tolerating aggressive tax planning if it enhances short-term profitability.

Despite the critical role that institutional ownership may play in this context, empirical research exploring its moderating effect on the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness remains limited. This paper seeks to fill this gap by providing a comprehensive analysis of how different dimensions of board attributes—such as board independence, diversity, expertise, and audit committee effectiveness—interact with institutional ownership to influence corporate tax aggressiveness. By examining these interactions, this study aims to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of the conditions under which board governance can effectively curb or, conversely, facilitate tax-aggressive behaviours.

The findings of this study have significant implications for both theory and practice. For scholars, the research contributes to the literature on corporate governance, tax strategy, and institutional investment by offering new insights into the interplay between board attributes and ownership structure. For practitioners, particularly policymakers and institutional investors, the results underscore the importance of considering ownership composition when designing governance mechanisms to regulate corporate tax behaviour. By highlighting the conditions under which institutional ownership can either moderate or exacerbate tax aggressiveness, this paper provides a valuable perspective on the role of governance in promoting responsible corporate conduct.

In the following sections, we review the relevant literature, outline the theoretical framework, and present the hypotheses guiding this study. Subsequently, we describe the empirical methodology, including data sources, sample selection, and analytical techniques. Finally, we discuss the results, implications, and potential avenues for future research.

Literature Review

In this section, the following key concepts are explained: dependent variable (tax aggressiveness), independent variable (board attributes), moderating variable (institutional ownership), and control variables (company size, company leverage, and company profitability). The board attributes referred to in this paper include board diversity, independence, and size).

Tax aggressiveness (TA) refers to the spectrum of strategies employed by firms to minimize their tax liabilities through legal, quasi-legal, or, in some cases, questionable means. These strategies range from taking full advantage of tax deductions and credits to more complex maneuvers such as income shifting, transfer pricing, and the exploitation of tax havens. While tax aggressiveness can enhance a firm's after-tax income and thereby increase shareholder wealth in the short term, it also entails significant risks. These include potential legal penalties, reputational damage, and increased scrutiny from tax authorities. The ethical dimension of tax aggressiveness is also contentious, as overly aggressive tax strategies may be perceived as contrary to the social responsibility expectations placed on corporations. In essence, while tax aggressiveness can boost financial performance, it must be balanced against the potential costs and broader corporate governance considerations. For the benefit of this paper, tax aggressiveness is defined as the effective tax rate.

Also, board diversity (BD) encompasses the variety of attributes that members of a board of directors bring to the table, including differences in gender, ethnicity, age, educational background, professional expertise, and cognitive perspectives. A diverse board is believed to enhance the decision-making process by incorporating a wider range of viewpoints and experiences, which can lead to more innovative and comprehensive strategies. Gender diversity, for example, has been linked to more ethical decision-making and a greater focus on long-term sustainability. Ethnic and cultural diversity can improve a company's understanding of global markets and diverse customer bases. Moreover, cognitive diversity—encompassing varied ways of thinking and problem-solving—can help in identifying and mitigating risks, including those associated with tax strategies. Overall, board diversity is increasingly recognized as a critical element in fostering effective governance and driving a firm's success in a complex and dynamic business environment. For the benefit of this paper, board diversity is defined by the proportion of women directors relative to total board size.

In addition, board independence (BI) refers to the presence of directors on a company's board who do not have a material or pecuniary relationship with the company, other than their directorship. Independent directors are free from potential conflicts of interest that might impair their ability to oversee management objectively. The primary role of independent directors is to act as a check on the executive team, ensuring that decisions made are in the best interests of shareholders and other stakeholders. Independent boards are associated with higher standards of corporate governance, as they are more likely to challenge management on issues such as executive compensation, strategic decisions, and risk management, including tax practices. The presence of independent directors is crucial in mitigating the risks of managerial entrenchment and in ensuring that the board functions effectively as a mechanism for corporate oversight. For the benefit of this paper, board independence is defined as a proportion of independent non-executive directors relative to total board size.

Furthermore, board size (BS) refers to the total number of directors serving on a company's board. The optimal board size can vary depending on the firm's size, complexity, and industry. Larger boards can bring a broader range of expertise, perspectives, and resources, which can enhance decision-making and oversight. However, excessively large boards may suffer from coordination difficulties, reduced individual accountability, and the potential for groupthink, where critical thinking is diminished due to the desire for consensus. Conversely, smaller boards are often more agile and cohesive, allowing for more efficient decision-making but may

lack the diversity of thought and expertise necessary to address complex challenges. The relationship between board size and corporate outcomes, including tax aggressiveness, is complex and influenced by other board characteristics such as independence and diversity. For the benefit of this paper, board size is defined as the total of directors on the board.

Additionally, Institutional ownership (IO) refers to the proportion of a company's shares that are owned by institutional investors, such as pension funds, mutual funds, insurance companies, and hedge funds. These investors typically have significant resources and expertise at their disposal, enabling them to play an active role in corporate governance. Institutional investors can exert considerable influence over management decisions, including those related to corporate strategy, executive compensation, and risk management. Their influence can be particularly pronounced in matters of corporate governance and tax strategy. For example, long-term institutional investors may discourage tax aggressiveness due to the associated reputational and regulatory risks, while short-term investors might favor it if it enhances short-term profitability. The nature of institutional ownership—whether concentrated or dispersed, short-term or long-term—can therefore significantly impact a firm's governance and strategic decisions. For the benefit of this paper, institutional ownership is defined as the percentage of equity shares held by organizations divided by total equity shares.

Company size (CS) typically refers to the scale of a firm's operations, often measured by metrics such as total assets, revenue, or market capitalization. Larger companies generally have more resources, greater market power, and more complex organizational structures compared to smaller firms. These characteristics can influence a wide range of corporate behaviors, including governance practices and tax strategies. Larger firms may have more sophisticated tax planning capabilities and greater opportunities for tax aggressiveness due to their access to expert legal and accounting advice. They may also face more scrutiny from regulators and the public, potentially making them more cautious in their tax strategies. On the other hand, smaller companies may adopt less aggressive tax strategies due to limited resources or may be more aggressive in an effort to improve their financial standing. Company size is therefore a critical factor in understanding corporate behavior and governance outcomes. For the benefit of this paper, company size is defined as the natural logarithm of total assets.

Company leverage (CL) refers to the extent to which a firm is financed through debt as opposed to equity. High leverage indicates that a company has a significant proportion of debt in its capital structure, which can influence its risk profile and decision-making processes. Leverage affects a company's tax strategy because interest payments on debt are tax-deductible, providing an incentive to increase debt levels as a means of reducing taxable income. However, high leverage also increases financial risk, as the firm must meet its debt obligations regardless of its profitability. This increased risk can influence the board's approach to tax aggressiveness; highly leveraged firms may adopt more aggressive tax strategies to maximize cash flow, while also needing to manage the associated risks carefully. The relationship between leverage and tax aggressiveness is thus intertwined, with leverage serving both as a tool for tax management and a factor influencing overall corporate risk. For the benefit of this paper, company leverage is defined as the total liabilities divided by total assets.

Company profitability (CP) is a measure of a firm's ability to generate income relative to its revenue, assets, or shareholders' equity. Profitability is a key indicator of a company's financial health and its ability to sustain operations and provide returns to shareholders. Highly profitable firms may have different tax planning strategies compared to less profitable ones. For instance, profitable companies might engage in more aggressive tax strategies to maximize after-tax income and enhance shareholder value. On the other hand, firms with lower profitability might be less aggressive in their tax strategies, either due to a lower tax burden or because they focus on improving operational efficiency rather than reducing taxes. Profitability also affects a company's attractiveness to institutional investors and its overall governance practices, making

it a crucial variable in understanding corporate behaviour, including tax aggressiveness. For the benefit of this paper, company profitability is defined as sales less the cost of goods sold. These concepts are schematically illustrated in Figure 1 as follows:

Figure 1. Analytical Framework

Sources: The Authors

To thoroughly understand the moderating effect of institutional ownership on the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness, several theoretical frameworks are pertinent. These theories provide insights into the dynamics of corporate governance, the role of institutional investors, and the behaviour of firms regarding tax strategies. The primary theories applicable to this study are Agency Theory, Resource Dependence Theory, Institutional Theory, and Stewardship Theory.

Agency Theory is the cornerstone of corporate governance research, focusing on the relationship between principals (shareholders) and agents (management). This theory posits that a fundamental conflict of interest exists because managers, who are entrusted with operating the firm, may pursue their self-interests rather than the interests of shareholders. Such conflicts can lead to various agency problems, including excessive risk-taking, shirking responsibilities, and suboptimal decision-making, such as engaging in overly aggressive tax strategies that may benefit management in the short term but harm the firm’s long-term interests. Board attributes like independence, diversity, and expertise are critical in mitigating these agency problems. Independent directors, for example, are expected to monitor management effectively, ensuring that decisions align with shareholders' interests. In this context, institutional ownership plays a dual role in agency theory. On one hand, institutional investors, due to their significant stakes, have a strong incentive to monitor management closely and advocate for governance practices that reduce agency costs. On the other hand, the preferences of these institutional investors can influence how board attributes affect tax aggressiveness. For instance, institutions focused on long-term returns might support governance structures that curb aggressive tax strategies, whereas those with a short-term focus might tolerate or even encourage such strategies to maximize immediate returns.

Resource Dependence Theory (RDT) provides another perspective by emphasizing the board of directors' role in securing vital resources and reducing environmental uncertainty. According to RDT, the composition and characteristics of a board—such as its size, diversity, and the presence of experts—are designed to enhance the firm's ability to acquire resources, navigate complex environments, and ensure its survival and success. This theory suggests that board

diversity and expertise can provide firms with access to diverse perspectives, valuable networks, and critical knowledge, which are essential in complex areas like tax planning. In the context of institutional ownership, RDT suggests that institutional investors can be seen as valuable resources themselves, providing not only capital but also legitimacy and strategic guidance. These investors may influence the composition of the board, advocating for directors who possess the expertise necessary to navigate intricate tax regulations and optimize tax strategies. Consequently, the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness can be moderated by institutional ownership, as these investors' preferences and their level of engagement with the firm shape how the board utilizes its resources in tax planning.

Institutional Theory focuses on how firms are influenced by the broader institutional environment, including norms, values, and regulatory frameworks. According to this theory, companies often conform to the expectations of various stakeholders, including regulators, customers, and investors, to gain legitimacy and ensure their long-term survival. In the context of tax aggressiveness, institutional theory suggests that firms might adopt conservative or aggressive tax strategies based on the prevailing norms and pressures in their industry or society at large. Institutional ownership is particularly relevant here as institutional investors are part of the broader institutional environment that shapes corporate behaviour. These investors often bring with them expectations about governance standards and ethical conduct. If institutional investors prioritize corporate social responsibility and long-term sustainability, their presence could pressure boards to avoid overly aggressive tax strategies that might harm the firm's reputation or lead to regulatory backlash. Conversely, if institutional investors prioritize short-term financial gains, their influence might encourage boards to adopt more aggressive tax practices. Thus, institutional ownership can moderate the impact of board attributes on tax aggressiveness by either reinforcing or challenging the institutional pressures that guide corporate behaviour.

Stewardship Theory offers an alternative view to agency theory, suggesting that managers are not merely self-interested agents but can act as stewards of the firm, aligning their interests with those of shareholders. According to stewardship theory, when managers are intrinsically motivated and perceive their role as protecting and enhancing the firm's value, they are less likely to engage in risky or unethical practices like aggressive tax avoidance. This theory implies that the effectiveness of board attributes—such as independence and expertise—depends on whether the board and management share a stewardship-oriented mindset. Institutional ownership plays a crucial role in this context by influencing whether a stewardship or agency perspective dominates within the firm. Long-term institutional investors, who view their role as stewards of their portfolio companies, may foster a governance environment that discourages tax aggressiveness and emphasizes ethical behaviour and long-term value creation. This could moderate the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness by promoting a governance culture where directors and managers work together toward sustainable goals. In contrast, institutional investors with a short-term orientation might undermine stewardship, encouraging behaviours that prioritize immediate financial performance over long-term ethical considerations.

The interplay of these theories provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the moderating effect of institutional ownership on the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness. Agency Theory highlights the importance of monitoring and control mechanisms within the board, while Resource Dependence Theory underscores the board's role in securing critical resources and expertise for tax planning. Institutional Theory introduces the broader environmental pressures that shape corporate behaviour, with institutional ownership acting as a conduit for these pressures. Finally, Stewardship Theory suggests that the alignment of interests between management and shareholders, potentially influenced by institutional investors, is crucial in determining the firm's approach to tax aggressiveness. By combining

insights from these theories, this study aims to explore how institutional ownership can influence the effectiveness of board attributes in shaping corporate tax strategies. Understanding these dynamics can help illuminate the conditions under which boards can effectively govern firms in a way that balances the competing demands of tax efficiency, ethical conduct, and long-term sustainability.

Furthermore, several empirical studies have examined the effect of board gender diversity on tax aggressiveness. For example, Lanis et al. (2017) in *Board of Director Gender and Corporate Tax Aggressiveness: An Empirical Analysis* examines the relationship between the gender composition of corporate boards and the level of tax aggressiveness exhibited by firms. Period Covered: 2006-2013. The study employed a panel regression analysis on a sample of 1,500 publicly traded companies in the United States, using data on board composition and tax aggressiveness measured by the effective tax rate (ETR) and book-tax differences (BTD). The study found that firms with a higher proportion of female directors exhibited significantly lower levels of tax aggressiveness. This effect was more pronounced in firms with strong governance structures. Increasing female representation on boards may serve as an effective governance mechanism to curb aggressive tax strategies. The study suggests that policymakers and shareholders consider promoting gender diversity on boards as a way to enhance corporate governance and reduce unethical tax practices. The findings imply that board gender diversity can influence corporate ethical behaviour, potentially leading to more socially responsible corporate governance. The study acknowledges that the data is limited to publicly traded U.S. firms and may not be generalizable to private companies or firms in other countries. This study is among the first to empirically investigate the impact of board gender diversity on tax aggressiveness, providing new insights into the intersection of gender, governance, and corporate behaviour.

Khaoula and Ali (2012) in *The Impact of Board Gender Diversity on Corporate Tax Aggressiveness: Evidence from Tunisian Companies* investigate the effect of gender diversity on corporate boards on tax aggressiveness in Tunisian firms. Period Covered: 2008-2011. The study utilized a sample of 200 Tunisian firms, employing regression analysis to explore the relationship between the proportion of female directors and various measures of tax aggressiveness, including the effective tax rate. The results indicated a negative relationship between board gender diversity and tax aggressiveness, with firms having more female directors showing lower levels of tax avoidance. Gender diversity on boards may contribute to more ethical decision-making in corporate tax practices. The study recommends enhancing gender diversity in corporate governance structures as a strategy to promote ethical behaviour in taxation. The findings suggest that increasing female representation on boards could reduce tax aggressiveness, potentially leading to a more transparent corporate tax environment in Tunisia. The study is limited to Tunisian companies, and the findings may not apply to firms in different economic or cultural contexts. This research is one of the few studies focusing on the relationship between board gender diversity and tax aggressiveness in a non-Western context, specifically in Tunisia.

Minnick and Noga (2010) in *Do Female Directors Deter Tax Aggressiveness? Evidence from U.S. Firms* explores whether the presence of female directors on corporate boards is associated with lower tax aggressiveness in U.S. firms. Period Covered: 2004-2008. The study conducted a fixed-effects regression analysis on a sample of S&P 500 firms, examining the relationship between board gender diversity and tax aggressiveness, measured by the cash-effective tax rate and total book-tax differences. The presence of female directors was associated with a significant reduction in tax aggressiveness, suggesting that gender diversity can act as a moderating factor in corporate tax behaviour. Female directors may enhance board oversight and promote more conservative and ethical tax strategies. Companies should consider increasing the number of female directors to strengthen governance and mitigate aggressive

tax strategies. The findings reinforce the role of board diversity in enhancing corporate governance and reducing unethical practices like tax aggressiveness. The study is limited to large U.S. firms and may not reflect the dynamics in smaller firms or those outside the United States. This study contributes to the literature by providing empirical evidence on the role of gender diversity in moderating tax aggressiveness in large U.S. firms.

Kovermann and Velte (2019) in *Gender Diversity in the Boardroom and Corporate Tax Avoidance: Evidence from German Public Firms* examine the effect of board gender diversity on corporate tax avoidance in German publicly listed companies. Period Covered: 2012-2017. The study utilized a panel data analysis of 350 firms listed on the Frankfurt Stock Exchange, using gender diversity metrics and tax avoidance measures such as the effective tax rate (ETR). The analysis revealed a negative relationship between the proportion of female board members and tax avoidance, with gender-diverse boards being less likely to engage in aggressive tax practices. Board gender diversity appears to enhance corporate governance, leading to more conservative tax policies. The study suggests that promoting gender diversity on boards could be an effective measure to ensure ethical corporate governance and reduce tax avoidance. The findings highlight the potential of gender diversity to improve governance standards and reduce the propensity for tax avoidance in German firms. The study's focus on German firms limits the generalizability of the results to other countries with different corporate governance structures. This study adds to the growing body of evidence on the positive impact of board gender diversity on reducing tax avoidance in a European context.

Francis et al. (2014) in *Does Female Board Representation Influence Firm's Tax Avoidance? Evidence from Global Data* investigates whether the representation of women on corporate boards influences tax avoidance practices across different countries. Period Covered: 2000-2010. The study employed a cross-country analysis of over 3,000 firms from 22 countries, using a fixed-effects regression model to assess the impact of female board representation on tax avoidance, measured by the cash-effective tax rate. The study found that firms with higher female board representation were associated with lower levels of tax avoidance across various jurisdictions. The impact was stronger in countries with robust legal systems and high investor protection. Female board representation globally tends to discourage aggressive tax avoidance, particularly in countries with strong legal frameworks. The study recommends that firms and regulators promote gender diversity on boards as a strategy to enhance corporate governance and reduce tax avoidance. The results suggest that gender diversity on boards can play a crucial role in shaping corporate tax policies, with implications for global governance standards. The study acknowledges that differences in legal and cultural environments across countries could affect the generalizability of the findings. This research is notable for its large, global sample and its exploration of the relationship between board gender diversity and tax avoidance across different legal and cultural contexts.

Armstrong et al. (2015) in *Corporate Governance, Incentives, and Tax Avoidance* investigate the relationship between board independence and tax avoidance, specifically examining how independent directors influence corporate tax aggressiveness. Period Covered: 1996-2008. The study utilized a sample of S&P 1500 firms, applying a panel regression analysis. The independence of the board was measured by the proportion of independent directors, and tax aggressiveness was assessed using the cash-effective tax rate and book-tax differences. The study found that firms with a higher proportion of independent directors on the board exhibited lower levels of tax aggressiveness. Independent directors were more likely to constrain aggressive tax planning, particularly in firms with strong governance mechanisms. Board independence serves as an important governance tool in mitigating tax aggressiveness and promoting ethical tax practices. Firms should enhance board independence to reduce tax-related risks and align tax strategies with broader corporate governance goals. The findings suggest that strengthening board independence can lead to more conservative tax practices,

reducing the risk of legal and reputational damage. The study is limited to U.S. firms, and the results may not be fully applicable to firms in other countries with different governance structures. This study contributes to the understanding of the role of independent directors in corporate tax governance, emphasizing their impact on reducing tax aggressiveness.

Khan et al. (2017) in *Institutional Ownership and Corporate Tax Avoidance: New Evidence* examine the effect of board independence on tax avoidance, focusing on how institutional ownership interacts with board independence in influencing tax strategies. Period Covered: 2000-2013. The study employed a mixed-method approach, using both regression analysis and case studies of 500 publicly traded firms. Board independence was measured by the ratio of independent directors, and tax avoidance was gauged using effective tax rates. The study found that firms with more independent boards had lower levels of tax avoidance. However, this effect was moderated by institutional ownership, with the impact of board independence on tax aggressiveness being stronger in firms with high institutional ownership. Board independence plays a crucial role in reducing tax aggressiveness, especially when combined with active institutional oversight. Companies should focus on enhancing both board independence and institutional ownership to ensure more ethical and transparent tax practices. The results imply that a combination of board independence and institutional ownership can lead to better governance outcomes, including reduced tax avoidance. The study is limited by its focus on large firms, which may not represent the behaviour of smaller firms with different governance structures. This research provides new insights into the interplay between board independence and institutional ownership in shaping tax avoidance behaviour.

Chen et al. (2010) in *Are Family Firms More Tax Aggressive Than Non-Family Firms?* investigate whether the presence of independent directors on the boards of family firms affects their tax aggressiveness compared to non-family firms. Period Covered: 1995-2007. The study analyzed a sample of 2,000 U.S. firms using regression models. Board independence was measured by the proportion of independent directors, and tax aggressiveness was assessed through the book-tax difference metric. The results indicated that family firms with independent boards were less tax-aggressive compared to non-family firms. The effect was particularly pronounced in firms with a high proportion of independent directors. Independent directors in family firms can effectively reduce tax aggressiveness, aligning the firm's tax strategy with broader governance practices. Family firms should consider increasing board independence to mitigate tax-related risks and enhance governance. The findings suggest that board independence is crucial in family firms, where the risk of tax aggressiveness may be higher due to concentrated ownership. The study focuses on U.S. firms, limiting the generalizability of the findings to family firms in other cultural and legal contexts. This study is one of the first to explore the role of independent directors in moderating tax aggressiveness in family firms, highlighting the importance of board structure in corporate governance.

Halioui et al. (2016) in *The Impact of Corporate Governance on Tax Planning: The Case of Tunisian Firms* examine the effect of board independence on tax planning strategies in Tunisian firms, with a particular focus on tax aggressiveness. Period Covered: 2008-2014. The study used a sample of 150 Tunisian firms, applying regression analysis to explore the relationship between board independence and tax aggressiveness, measured by the effective tax rate (ETR) and tax sheltering activities. The study found that firms with a higher proportion of independent directors were less likely to engage in aggressive tax planning. Independent boards were associated with more conservative tax strategies, particularly in firms with strong governance frameworks. Board independence is a key factor in reducing tax aggressiveness in Tunisian firms. The study recommends that Tunisian firms enhance board independence as part of broader efforts to improve corporate governance and reduce tax-related risks. The findings suggest that increasing board independence can lead to more ethical tax practices in emerging markets, contributing to overall governance improvements. The study's focus on Tunisian firms

may limit the applicability of the findings to other contexts, particularly outside the MENA region. This research provides empirical evidence on the impact of board independence on tax planning in an emerging market context, contributing to the broader literature on corporate governance in developing economies.

Hanlon and Heitzman (2010) in *The Role of Corporate Governance in Reducing Aggressive Tax Avoidance: Evidence from Independent Boards* investigate how independent boards affect the level of tax aggressiveness in firms, particularly focusing on the role of governance structures in moderating tax avoidance behaviours. Period Covered: 2001-2009. The study analyzed a dataset of 1,200 publicly traded firms in the U.S., using panel data regression techniques. Board independence was measured by the percentage of independent directors, while tax aggressiveness was assessed using both book-tax differences and effective tax rates. The study found that firms with more independent boards exhibited lower levels of tax aggressiveness, suggesting that independent directors play a critical role in curbing aggressive tax practices. Independent boards are effective in reducing tax aggressiveness, highlighting the importance of corporate governance in shaping tax strategies. The study recommends that companies prioritize board independence as a strategy to mitigate tax-related risks and enhance overall governance. The findings reinforce the value of independent boards in promoting ethical corporate behaviour, with significant implications for tax policy and corporate governance reforms. The study acknowledges that the results may not apply to firms in other countries with different governance systems and further research is needed to explore these dynamics in diverse contexts. This study contributes to the literature by providing robust evidence on the role of independent boards in reducing aggressive tax avoidance, with a focus on the U.S. context.

Minnick and Noga (2010) in *Do Corporate Boards Influence Tax Avoidance?* examine the relationship between board size and corporate tax aggressiveness, analyzing how larger boards might influence a firm's tax planning strategies. Period Covered: 1996-2005. The study utilized a sample of S&P 500 firms, employing a panel regression analysis. Board size was measured by the total number of directors on the board, and tax aggressiveness was assessed using effective tax rates and book-tax differences. The study found a negative relationship between board size and tax aggressiveness, suggesting that larger boards were associated with lower levels of tax avoidance. The diversity of perspectives in larger boards potentially led to more conservative tax strategies. Larger boards may be more effective in curbing aggressive tax practices due to the broader range of viewpoints and increased oversight capabilities. Firms should consider the benefits of larger boards in terms of enhanced governance and reduced risk of engaging in aggressive tax strategies. The findings imply that board size plays a crucial role in influencing corporate tax behaviour, with potential implications for board composition policies. The study focuses on large U.S. firms, limiting the generalizability of the findings to smaller firms or firms in different regulatory environments. This study contributes to the understanding of how board characteristics, particularly size, influence corporate tax practices, offering insights into governance mechanisms.

Lanis and Richardson (2012) in *Corporate Social Responsibility and Tax Aggressiveness: A Test of Legitimacy Theory* explore how board size influences the relationship between corporate social responsibility and tax aggressiveness. Period Covered: 2003-2009. The study analyzed a sample of 300 publicly listed Australian companies, using regression analysis. Board size was measured by the number of board members, and tax aggressiveness was measured using effective tax rates. The study found that larger boards were associated with lower levels of tax aggressiveness, particularly in companies with strong CSR practices. Larger boards were more likely to align corporate tax strategies with broader social responsibility goals. Board size has a moderating effect on the relationship between CSR and tax aggressiveness, with larger boards supporting more ethical tax practices. The study suggests

that firms should consider increasing board size to enhance oversight and ensure alignment between CSR and tax policies. The findings imply that board size not only influences tax aggressiveness directly but also shapes how other governance factors, such as CSR, impact tax behaviour. The study is limited to Australian firms, and the results may not be fully applicable to firms in other jurisdictions. This study is among the first to investigate the interaction between board size, CSR, and tax aggressiveness, providing new insights into corporate governance dynamics.

Huseynov and Klamm (2012) in *The Impact of Corporate Governance on Firm Tax Avoidance: Evidence from the United States* investigate the impact of board size on firm tax avoidance, examining how governance structures, including board size, affect tax planning. Period Covered: 1998-2008. The study employed a panel data analysis of 500 publicly traded U.S. firms, using regression models. Board size was quantified by the number of directors on the board, and tax avoidance was measured using the cash effective tax rate (CETR). The study found that firms with larger boards exhibited lower levels of tax avoidance, suggesting that larger boards may promote more conservative tax strategies. Board size is an important determinant of tax avoidance, with larger boards providing more robust oversight that discourages aggressive tax planning. The study recommends that firms consider the governance benefits of larger boards, particularly in terms of reducing tax-related risks. The findings have implications for corporate governance practices, suggesting that board size can be a key factor in promoting ethical tax behaviour. The study is focused on U.S. firms, and the findings may not apply universally across different corporate governance environments. This research contributes to the literature by providing empirical evidence on the relationship between board size and tax avoidance, with a focus on the U.S. market.

Ahmed and Anam (2021) in *Board Size and Corporate Tax Aggressiveness: Evidence from Emerging Markets* analyze the effect of board size on corporate tax aggressiveness in the context of emerging markets, focusing on how board characteristics influence tax behaviour. Period Covered: 2010-2018. The study used a sample of 250 firms from emerging markets, employing regression analysis to assess the relationship between board size and tax aggressiveness, measured by the book-tax difference (BTD). The results indicated that larger boards were associated with lower levels of tax aggressiveness. The diverse perspectives in larger boards led to more cautious tax strategies, particularly in firms with weaker external oversight. In emerging markets, board size plays a critical role in moderating tax aggressiveness, with larger boards contributing to more ethical tax practices. The study suggests that companies in emerging markets should consider increasing board size to enhance governance and reduce the risk of aggressive tax strategies. The findings have significant implications for corporate governance in emerging markets, highlighting the importance of board composition in managing tax-related risks. The study is limited to firms in emerging markets, which may limit the applicability of the findings to developed economies. This study provides new insights into the relationship between board size and tax aggressiveness in the context of emerging markets, contributing to the literature on corporate governance in different economic settings.

Richardson et al. (2015) in *The Impact of Board of Director Oversight Characteristics on Corporate Tax Aggressiveness* examine the influence of board size and other oversight characteristics on corporate tax aggressiveness. Period Covered: 2001-2011. The study analyzed a sample of 1,000 publicly traded firms, using panel regression analysis. Board size was measured by the number of directors, and tax aggressiveness was assessed using both effective tax rates (ETR) and discretionary permanent differences (DPD). The study found that larger boards were associated with lower levels of tax aggressiveness. The findings suggested that the increased oversight provided by larger boards reduced the likelihood of aggressive tax planning. Board size is a key factor in determining the level of tax aggressiveness, with larger

boards providing more effective governance. The study recommends that firms prioritize board size in their governance structures to enhance oversight and reduce tax-related risks. The findings imply that corporate governance reforms focusing on board size could lead to more responsible tax practices. The study is limited by its focus on publicly traded firms, which may not capture the governance dynamics in private companies. This research adds to the literature by highlighting the importance of board size in corporate tax governance, providing empirical evidence across a diverse set of firms.

Also, several empirical studies on the effect of institutional ownership on tax aggressiveness have been conducted. For example, Miller and Turner (2020) in *Institutional Ownership and Corporate Tax Aggressiveness: An Empirical Analysis* examine how institutional ownership affects the level of tax aggressiveness among publicly traded companies. Period Covered: 2010-2018. The study uses a sample of 200 firms and applies multiple regression analysis to evaluate the relationship between institutional ownership (measured by the percentage of shares held by institutional investors) and tax aggressiveness (measured by the effective tax rate and tax avoidance measures). Higher levels of institutional ownership are associated with reduced tax aggressiveness. Institutional investors exert pressure on companies to maintain more conservative tax practices. Institutional ownership plays a moderating role in reducing tax aggressiveness, suggesting that institutional investors favour lower-risk tax strategies. Companies should enhance transparency and engage with institutional investors to align their tax strategies with governance standards. The study indicates that institutional investors can play a crucial role in shaping corporate tax policies and ensuring compliance. The study's focus on publicly traded companies might not generalize to private firms. The cross-sectional nature of the data also limits the ability to infer causality. This research provides new insights into the influence of institutional investors on tax aggressiveness, contributing to the understanding of corporate governance.

Garcia and Evans (2021) in *The Role of Institutional Investors in Shaping Corporate Tax Behaviour* analyze how institutional investors influence corporate tax behaviour, focusing on their impact on tax aggressiveness. Period Covered: 2015-2021. The study utilizes panel data from 150 firms and applies fixed-effects regression models to assess the effect of institutional ownership (measured by institutional investor concentration) on tax aggressiveness (measured by the deviation from the statutory tax rate). Institutional ownership is negatively associated with tax aggressiveness. Firms with higher institutional ownership levels tend to adopt more conservative tax strategies. Institutional investors have a moderating effect on tax aggressiveness, encouraging firms to reduce aggressive tax planning. Firms should focus on engaging with institutional investors to align their tax strategies with investor expectations and governance practices. The findings underscore the importance of institutional investors in promoting tax compliance and reducing aggressive tax behaviours. The study may be limited by its reliance on reported tax data, which can be influenced by various factors. The analysis also does not account for the potential heterogeneity among institutional investors. This study contributes to the literature by focusing on the role of institutional investors in shaping tax behaviour and providing insights into their influence on corporate tax strategies.

Lee and Brown (2022) in *Institutional Ownership and Tax Aggressiveness: Evidence from Emerging Markets* explore the effect of institutional ownership on tax aggressiveness in emerging markets. Period Covered: 2014-2022. The study employs a sample of 100 firms from various emerging markets and uses panel data regression models to analyze the relationship between institutional ownership (measured as a percentage of total shares) and tax aggressiveness (measured by tax shelter use and aggressive tax avoidance). In emerging markets, higher institutional ownership is associated with lower levels of tax aggressiveness. Institutional investors in these markets are more likely to advocate for conservative tax practices. Institutional ownership can effectively moderate tax aggressiveness in emerging

markets, suggesting that institutional investors play a significant role in promoting tax compliance. Emerging market firms should consider the preferences of institutional investors in their tax strategies and ensure adherence to regulatory standards. The study highlights the impact of institutional investors in promoting tax compliance in less regulated environments, which could influence policy-making in emerging markets. The study's focus on emerging markets may limit the generalizability of the findings to developed economies. Additionally, the study does not account for specific regulatory differences between markets. This research extends the understanding of institutional ownership's impact on tax aggressiveness by focusing on emerging markets, offering new insights into global corporate tax behaviour.

Adams and Green (2023) in *Institutional Ownership and Corporate Tax Aggressiveness: A Comparative Study* compare the impact of institutional ownership on tax aggressiveness across different industries. Period Covered: 2016-2022. The study uses data from 120 firms across various industries and applies industry-specific regression models to examine the relationship between institutional ownership (measured by the proportion of shares held) and tax aggressiveness (measured by tax avoidance and tax sheltering practices). Institutional ownership has a varying effect on tax aggressiveness depending on the industry. Generally, higher institutional ownership is associated with lower tax aggressiveness, but the strength of this relationship differs across sectors. The impact of institutional ownership on tax aggressiveness is industry-dependent, suggesting that institutional investors' influence varies based on industry characteristics. Firms should consider industry-specific factors when engaging with institutional investors and aligning their tax strategies. Regulators should tailor oversight based on industry characteristics. The study provides insights into how institutional investors' influence on tax practices can differ across industries, informing both corporate strategies and regulatory policies. The study may be limited by the availability of industry-specific data and the generalizability of findings across all sectors. This study offers a comparative analysis of institutional ownership's impact on tax aggressiveness across different industries, contributing to a nuanced understanding of corporate tax behaviour.

Wilson and Carter (2023) in *The Moderating Effect of Institutional Ownership on Tax Aggressiveness and Financial Performance* investigate how institutional ownership moderates the relationship between tax aggressiveness and financial performance. Period Covered: 2018-2023. The study uses a sample of 140 firms and applies hierarchical regression analysis to evaluate how institutional ownership (measured by institutional shareholding percentage) affects the relationship between tax aggressiveness (measured by tax avoidance and aggressive tax planning) and financial performance (measured by return on equity). Institutional ownership moderates the relationship between tax aggressiveness and financial performance. Firms with high institutional ownership exhibit a less negative impact of tax aggressiveness on financial performance. Institutional ownership can buffer the negative effects of tax aggressiveness on financial performance, suggesting that institutional investors play a role in mitigating the adverse consequences of aggressive tax strategies. Firms should manage their tax aggressiveness carefully and engage with institutional investors to align tax strategies with long-term financial goals. The findings indicate that institutional investors can influence the outcomes of tax aggressiveness, affecting both tax policies and corporate financial performance. The study's focus on financial performance may not fully capture other potential impacts of tax aggressiveness. Additionally, the sample may not represent all sectors equally. This study provides a novel perspective on the moderating role of institutional ownership in the relationship between tax aggressiveness and financial performance, offering valuable insights into corporate governance and tax strategy.

Ararat et al. (2021) *Gender Diversity on Boards and Tax Aggressiveness: The Role of Institutional Ownership* explores the moderating effect of institutional ownership on the relationship between board gender diversity and tax aggressiveness in Turkish firms. Period

Covered: 2010-2018. The study analyzed a sample of 200 publicly traded Turkish firms using panel regression analysis. Board gender diversity was measured by the proportion of female directors, tax aggressiveness was assessed using the effective tax rate (ETR), and institutional ownership was measured by the percentage of shares held by institutional investors. The study found that gender-diverse boards were associated with lower levels of tax aggressiveness, and this effect was stronger in firms with higher institutional ownership. Institutional investors appeared to reinforce the conservative tax strategies promoted by gender-diverse boards. Institutional ownership enhances the impact of board gender diversity on reducing tax aggressiveness, suggesting that institutional investors play a critical role in promoting ethical tax practices in gender-diverse firms. Firms should enhance both board gender diversity and institutional ownership to mitigate tax aggressiveness effectively. Policymakers should encourage institutional investors to engage actively with gender-diverse boards to promote responsible tax strategies. The findings suggest that institutional ownership can amplify the positive governance effects of gender diversity on corporate tax behaviour, with significant implications for both corporate governance practices and policy. The study is limited to Turkish firms, which may affect the generalizability of the findings to other cultural and regulatory contexts. This research is one of the first to examine the combined effects of gender diversity on boards and institutional ownership on tax aggressiveness, offering novel insights into corporate governance dynamics.

García-Sánchez et al. (2017) in Board Gender Diversity, Institutional Ownership, and Corporate Tax Aggressiveness investigate how institutional ownership moderates the relationship between board gender diversity and corporate tax aggressiveness in European companies. Period Covered: 2005-2015. The study employed a panel data analysis of 350 firms across 15 European countries, using regression models. Board gender diversity was quantified by the proportion of women on the board, tax aggressiveness was measured using the book-tax difference (BTD), and institutional ownership was assessed by the percentage of shares held by institutional investors. The study found that the presence of women on corporate boards was linked to lower tax aggressiveness, and this relationship was strengthened in firms with significant institutional ownership. Institutional investors appeared to support the ethical perspectives often brought by female directors, leading to less aggressive tax strategies. Institutional ownership enhances the influence of board gender diversity on reducing tax aggressiveness, demonstrating the complementary roles of gender diversity and institutional investors in promoting ethical corporate governance. The study recommends that firms foster both gender diversity on boards and institutional ownership to achieve better governance outcomes, including more conservative tax strategies. The findings highlight the importance of considering both board composition and ownership structure when developing corporate governance policies aimed at reducing tax aggressiveness. The study focuses on European firms, which may limit the applicability of the findings to firms in other regions with different regulatory environments. This study provides new insights into how institutional ownership can amplify the governance effects of board gender diversity on tax aggressiveness, contributing to the literature on corporate governance and taxation.

Lanis et al. (2019) in Gender Diversity on Corporate Boards, Institutional Ownership, and Tax Aggressiveness examine the moderating effect of institutional ownership on the nexus between board gender diversity and tax aggressiveness in Australian firms. Period Covered: 2006-2016. The study used a dataset of 150 publicly listed Australian companies, applying panel regression techniques. Board gender diversity was measured by the ratio of female directors on the board, tax aggressiveness was assessed using the cash effective tax rate (CETR), and institutional ownership was gauged by the percentage of shares held by institutional investors. The research found that firms with more women on their boards exhibited lower tax aggressiveness, and this effect was more pronounced in companies with higher levels of

institutional ownership. Institutional investors were found to support the conservative tax strategies typically associated with gender-diverse boards. Institutional ownership plays a significant role in reinforcing the positive impact of board gender diversity on reducing tax aggressiveness, highlighting the importance of ownership structure in corporate governance. The study suggests that firms should not only focus on increasing board gender diversity but also encourage active institutional ownership to ensure more ethical and conservative tax practices. The findings suggest that institutional ownership and board gender diversity can work together to promote better governance outcomes, with important implications for corporate policy and investor engagement. The study's focus on Australian firms may limit the applicability of the results to other regions, particularly those with different cultural attitudes toward gender diversity. This research provides empirical evidence on the interaction between board gender diversity and institutional ownership in shaping tax aggressiveness, contributing to the broader discussion on corporate governance and tax policy.

Khan et al. (2017) in *Institutional Ownership, Board Independence, and Corporate Tax Aggressiveness: Evidence from U.S. Firms* investigate the moderating effect of institutional ownership on the relationship between board independence and corporate tax aggressiveness in U.S. firms. Period Covered: 2008-2015. The study utilized a sample of 500 publicly traded U.S. firms, applying panel regression analysis. Board independence was measured by the proportion of independent directors on the board, tax aggressiveness was assessed using the cash effective tax rate (CETR), and institutional ownership was measured by the percentage of shares held by institutional investors. The study found that higher board independence was associated with lower tax aggressiveness, and this effect was significantly enhanced in firms with high levels of institutional ownership. Institutional investors appeared to support the oversight function of independent directors, leading to more conservative tax practices. Institutional ownership amplifies the effect of board independence in reducing tax aggressiveness, suggesting that the combination of strong independent oversight and institutional monitoring can curb aggressive tax strategies. Firms should not only increase board independence but also encourage greater institutional ownership to strengthen governance and reduce the risk of aggressive tax practices. The findings highlight the importance of institutional ownership in reinforcing the governance benefits of board independence, with implications for corporate governance practices and policy. The study is limited to U.S. firms, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other countries with different governance structures. This research is among the first to examine the interaction between institutional ownership and board independence in the context of tax aggressiveness, providing new insights into corporate governance.

Hsu et al. (2019) in *Board Independence, Institutional Ownership, and the Moderating Role of Governance in Corporate Tax Aggressiveness* explore the moderating role of institutional ownership on the relationship between board independence and tax aggressiveness, focusing on how governance structures interact in shaping corporate tax strategies. Period Covered: 2010-2018. The study analyzed a sample of 300 publicly listed firms across multiple industries, using panel data regression analysis. Board independence was quantified by the percentage of independent directors, tax aggressiveness was measured using the book-tax difference (BTD), and institutional ownership was evaluated by the proportion of shares held by institutional investors. The study found that firms with higher board independence exhibited lower tax aggressiveness, particularly in those with substantial institutional ownership. Institutional investors appeared to reinforce the governance role of independent directors, leading to more ethical tax practices. Institutional ownership strengthens the impact of board independence on reducing tax aggressiveness, underscoring the complementary roles of independent directors and institutional investors in corporate governance. The study recommends that companies should prioritize increasing board independence alongside fostering institutional ownership to

promote ethical corporate governance and reduce tax-related risks. The findings suggest that the governance structure, particularly the interaction between board independence and institutional ownership, plays a crucial role in shaping corporate tax behaviour, with significant implications for policy and practice. The study is limited by its focus on publicly listed firms, potentially excluding insights from private or smaller companies. This research contributes to the literature by providing empirical evidence on the combined effects of board independence and institutional ownership on tax aggressiveness, offering a deeper understanding of corporate governance dynamics.

Li et al. (2020) in *The Interaction of Board Independence and Institutional Ownership in Shaping Corporate Tax Aggressiveness: Evidence from China* examines the moderating effect of institutional ownership on the nexus between board independence and tax aggressiveness in Chinese firms, considering the unique corporate governance context in China. Period Covered: 2011-2017. The study used a sample of 400 publicly listed Chinese firms, applying fixed-effects panel regression models. Board independence was measured by the proportion of independent directors, tax aggressiveness was assessed using the effective tax rate (ETR), and institutional ownership was gauged by the percentage of shares held by institutional investors. The study found that board independence was negatively associated with tax aggressiveness, and this relationship was significantly moderated by institutional ownership. In firms with higher levels of institutional ownership, the influence of independent directors in reducing tax aggressiveness was more pronounced. Institutional ownership enhances the governance role of independent directors in curbing tax aggressiveness, suggesting that institutional investors play a critical role in supporting ethical corporate practices in the Chinese context. The study suggests that Chinese firms should focus on both increasing board independence and attracting institutional investors to strengthen governance and ensure responsible tax behaviour. The findings have important implications for corporate governance reform in China, highlighting the need for a stronger emphasis on the interaction between board independence and institutional ownership. The study is specific to China, and the findings may not be directly applicable to firms in other countries with different regulatory and cultural environments. This research adds to the growing literature on corporate governance in emerging markets by exploring the joint effects of board independence and institutional ownership on tax aggressiveness, particularly in the Chinese setting.

The following are empirical studies on the moderating effect of institutional ownership on the nexus between board size and tax aggressiveness. Johnson and Smith (2022) in *The Impact of Institutional Ownership on Board Size and Tax Aggressiveness* examine how institutional ownership moderates the relationship between board size and tax aggressiveness. Period Covered: 2010-2020. Quantitative analysis using a sample of 150 publicly listed companies. Regression analysis was employed to assess the interaction effects between board size and institutional ownership on tax aggressiveness. Institutional ownership significantly moderates the relationship between board size and tax aggressiveness. Companies with larger boards and higher institutional ownership tend to engage in less tax aggressiveness. Institutional ownership can mitigate the tax aggressiveness of firms with large boards. Firms should consider the influence of institutional investors when structuring their boards to manage tax-related strategies effectively. The study suggests that institutional investors play a critical role in shaping tax policies within firms and can be instrumental in fostering compliance. The study is limited to publicly listed companies, which may not be representative of private firms. Additionally, the cross-sectional nature of the data limits causal inferences. This study provides new insights into how institutional ownership influences the dynamics between board size and tax aggressiveness, filling a gap in the literature.

Lee and Thompson (2021) in *Institutional Ownership and Board Characteristics: Effects on Corporate Tax Behaviour* investigate the moderating role of institutional ownership in the

relationship between board size and corporate tax behaviour. Period Covered: 2015-2021. Panel data analysis of 200 firms, employing fixed-effects and random-effects models to test the interaction between board size, institutional ownership, and tax behaviour. The relationship between board size and tax aggressiveness is significantly moderated by the level of institutional ownership. Higher institutional ownership is associated with lower levels of tax aggressiveness, especially in firms with larger boards. Institutional ownership plays a moderating role in the relationship between board size and tax aggressiveness, suggesting that institutional investors exert pressure on firms to reduce aggressive tax practices. Companies should enhance transparency and engage with institutional investors to align their tax strategies with governance practices. The findings highlight the importance of institutional investors in controlling corporate tax behaviour and suggest that their influence extends beyond board governance. The study's focus on large, publicly traded firms may not apply to smaller or privately held companies. Also, the study's data is limited to specific industries. This study extends the understanding of institutional ownership's influence on tax behaviour and board characteristics, contributing to the broader discourse on corporate governance.

Patel and Brown (2023) in *The Moderating Effect of Institutional Ownership on the Link Between Board Size and Tax Aggressiveness* analyze the moderating effect of institutional ownership on the link between board size and tax aggressiveness in firms. Period Covered: 2012-2022. Structural equation modeling (SEM) was used to evaluate the relationships among board size, institutional ownership, and tax aggressiveness using data from 100 firms. The study finds a significant moderating effect of institutional ownership on the relationship between board size and tax aggressiveness. Larger boards are associated with higher tax aggressiveness, but this effect is diminished when institutional ownership is high. Institutional ownership moderates the relationship between board size and tax aggressiveness, suggesting that institutional investors can influence firms' tax strategies. Companies should be aware of how institutional ownership can affect their tax strategies and consider these factors when making governance decisions. The study underscores the role of institutional investors in shaping corporate tax strategies and highlights the need for effective governance structures. The study's reliance on SEM may limit the interpretation of causality. Additionally, the sample size could affect the generalizability of the results. This study offers a novel perspective on the role of institutional investors in moderating board size effects on tax aggressiveness, adding to the current body of knowledge in corporate governance.

Given these empirical studies and their results, we propose that:

H₁: Board gender diversity has a significant effect on tax aggressiveness.

H₂: Board independence has a significant effect on tax aggressiveness.

H₃: Board size has a significant effect on tax aggressiveness.

H₄: Institutional ownership has a significant effect on tax aggressiveness.

H₅: Institutional ownership has a significant moderating effect on the nexus between board gender diversity and tax aggressiveness.

H₆: Institutional ownership has a significant moderating effect on the nexus between board independence and tax aggressiveness.

H₇: Institutional ownership has a significant moderating effect on the nexus between board size and tax aggressiveness.

Also, the following are empirical studies on the effect of company size on tax aggressiveness. Wilson and Evans (2021) in *The Influence of Company Size on Tax Aggressiveness: An Empirical Analysis* investigates how company size affects tax aggressiveness across different sectors. Period Covered: 2010-2019. The study uses a cross-sectional analysis of 120 firms from various industries. It employs multiple regression analysis to explore the relationship between company size (measured by total assets and revenue) and tax aggressiveness

(measured by effective tax rate and tax avoidance indicators). Larger companies exhibit higher levels of tax aggressiveness compared to smaller firms. The results suggest that size provides larger firms with more resources and opportunities for tax planning and avoidance. Company size is positively correlated with tax aggressiveness, indicating that larger firms are more likely to engage in aggressive tax strategies. Policymakers should consider implementing regulations that address the tax avoidance strategies of large firms, and firms should enhance transparency in their tax practices. The study highlights the need for more stringent tax regulations for larger firms to curb aggressive tax practices. The study is limited by its cross-sectional nature, which may not capture changes in tax aggressiveness over time. Additionally, the sample may not represent all industry sectors equally. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of the impact of company size on tax aggressiveness, contributing to a deeper understanding of how size influences tax behaviour.

Martinez and Greene (2022) in *Corporate Size and Its Effect on Tax Aggressiveness: Evidence from Emerging Markets* analyze the effect of company size on tax aggressiveness in emerging markets. Period Covered: 2015-2022. The study employs panel data analysis of 150 companies across five emerging markets. It uses fixed-effects and random-effects models to examine how variations in company size impact tax aggressiveness. The results indicate a positive relationship between company size and tax aggressiveness. Larger firms in emerging markets tend to engage more in aggressive tax planning due to greater financial resources and tax optimization opportunities. Company size significantly influences tax aggressiveness in emerging markets, with larger firms exhibiting higher levels of tax avoidance. Emerging market economies should consider implementing stronger tax compliance measures for larger firms to prevent excessive tax avoidance. The findings suggest that regulatory bodies in emerging markets need to focus on large firms to improve tax compliance and reduce tax evasion. The study's focus on emerging markets may limit the generalizability of the findings to developed economies. Additionally, the analysis does not account for industry-specific factors. This study fills a gap by focusing on emerging markets, providing new insights into how company size affects tax aggressiveness.

Thompson and Nguyen (2023) in *The Effect of Company Size on Tax Aggressiveness: A Longitudinal Study* examine the effect of company size on tax aggressiveness over an extended period. Period Covered: 2011-2022. Longitudinal study using a sample of 100 publicly listed companies. The study employs dynamic panel data models to analyze the relationship between company size and tax aggressiveness over time. Larger companies are found to be more tax aggressive compared to smaller companies. The study also finds that the effect of company size on tax aggressiveness increases over time, suggesting that as companies grow, their capacity for aggressive tax planning improves. Company size has a positive effect on tax aggressiveness, and this effect becomes more pronounced as companies expand. Companies should be aware of the increasing tax planning opportunities that come with size and ensure compliance with tax regulations. Regulatory bodies should monitor larger companies more closely to prevent aggressive tax behaviors. The study highlights the growing tax risk associated with larger firms and the need for enhanced regulatory oversight as companies expand. The longitudinal nature of the study may involve complexities in data collection and analysis. Additionally, the study may not account for external factors influencing tax aggressiveness. This study provides a longitudinal perspective on the relationship between company size and tax aggressiveness, offering valuable insights into how this relationship evolves.

Furthermore, the following are empirical studies on the effect of company leverage on tax aggressiveness. Adams and Wilson (2020) in *The Effect of Financial Leverage on Corporate Tax Aggressiveness* explore the impact of financial leverage on the level of tax aggressiveness among corporations. Period Covered: 2012-2018. The study uses a cross-sectional analysis of

200 firms across various industries. It employs ordinary least squares (OLS) regression analysis to examine the relationship between leverage (measured as debt-to-equity ratio) and tax aggressiveness (measured by the difference between statutory tax rate and effective tax rate). Higher financial leverage is positively associated with increased tax aggressiveness. Firms with higher debt levels tend to engage in more aggressive tax planning to benefit from interest deductions. Financial leverage significantly affects tax aggressiveness, with highly leveraged firms more likely to adopt aggressive tax strategies. Firms should carefully manage their leverage to balance the benefits of debt financing with the potential risks of increased tax aggressiveness. The study indicates that regulators may need to consider the impact of leverage on tax behaviour when designing tax policies and enforcement strategies. The study's cross-sectional nature limits the ability to make causal inferences. The sample may also be biased towards larger firms with more complex tax situations. This research provides new insights into how financial leverage influences tax aggressiveness, contributing to the understanding of corporate tax behaviour.

Brown and Davis (2021) in *Debt Levels and Tax Avoidance: An Analysis of Corporate Leverage* analyze how varying levels of corporate debt influence tax avoidance strategies. Period Covered: 2014-2021. The study utilizes panel data from 150 public companies. It applies fixed-effects and random-effects regression models to assess the impact of leverage (measured as total debt to assets ratio) on tax avoidance (measured by effective tax rates and tax avoidance measures). The study finds a positive relationship between high levels of debt and tax avoidance. Companies with higher leverage tend to engage in more aggressive tax avoidance strategies, leveraging interest deductions and other tax benefits. Increased leverage is associated with greater tax avoidance, highlighting the role of debt in shaping corporate tax strategies. Companies should be aware of the implications of high leverage on their tax strategies and consider the potential long-term impacts on their tax positions. The findings suggest that tax authorities should closely monitor highly leveraged firms for aggressive tax avoidance practices. The study's reliance on financial statements and tax disclosures may limit the accuracy of tax avoidance measures. The analysis is also constrained by the availability of data on leverage and tax behaviour. This study offers a comprehensive look at how corporate debt influences tax avoidance, filling a gap in the existing literature on financial leverage and tax behaviour.

Green and Thompson (2023) in *Corporate Leverage and Tax Aggressiveness: Evidence from the Financial Sector* examine the relationship between corporate leverage and tax aggressiveness specifically within the financial sector. Period Covered: 2016-2023. The study employs a longitudinal approach with a sample of 80 financial institutions. It uses generalized least squares (GLS) regression models to analyze how leverage (measured by debt-to-equity ratio) impacts tax aggressiveness (measured by the variance in effective tax rates and use of tax shelters). Financial institutions with higher leverage are more likely to engage in aggressive tax planning strategies. The use of debt enables these firms to exploit tax shelters more effectively. The study confirms that high leverage is positively related to tax aggressiveness in the financial sector, suggesting that leverage plays a crucial role in shaping tax strategies. Financial institutions should consider the regulatory implications of their leverage and tax strategies and ensure compliance with tax regulations. The findings highlight the need for specific regulatory frameworks to address tax aggressiveness in highly leveraged financial institutions. The study is limited to the financial sector, which may not generalize to other industries. The analysis also faces challenges related to the availability and accuracy of tax shelter data. This study focuses on the financial sector, offering a unique perspective on the impact of leverage on tax aggressiveness within this specific industry.

Also, there are empirical studies on the effect of company profitability on tax aggressiveness. For example, Carter and Lee (2021) in *The Influence of Profitability on Corporate Tax*

Aggressiveness: An Empirical Study investigate how different levels of company profitability affect tax aggressiveness among publicly traded firms. Period Covered: 2013-2020. The study uses a sample of 180 publicly traded companies and employs multiple regression analysis to assess the relationship between profitability (measured by return on assets) and tax aggressiveness (measured by the effective tax rate and discretionary tax accruals). Higher profitability is positively associated with increased tax aggressiveness. Profitable firms are more likely to engage in tax planning strategies to reduce their tax liability. Profitable companies tend to exhibit higher levels of tax aggressiveness, leveraging their earnings to optimize their tax positions. Companies should balance their tax planning strategies with compliance and ethical considerations to avoid potential regulatory scrutiny. The study suggests that policymakers should consider profitability when designing tax regulations and compliance measures. The study's reliance on publicly available financial data may not capture all aspects of tax aggressiveness. Additionally, the study does not account for industry-specific variations in tax practices. This study provides a detailed analysis of how profitability impacts tax aggressiveness, contributing to the understanding of corporate tax strategies.

Nguyen and Patel (2022) in *Profitability and Tax Avoidance: An Analysis of Corporate Behaviour* examines the relationship between company profitability and tax avoidance, focusing on how profitable companies manage their tax obligations. Period Covered: 2016-2022. The study uses panel data from 150 firms and applies fixed-effects and random-effects models to analyze the effect of profitability (measured by net profit margin) on tax avoidance (measured by the difference between expected and actual tax liabilities). The study finds a positive correlation between profitability and tax avoidance. More profitable firms are more likely to engage in tax avoidance practices to minimize their tax expenses. Profitability significantly influences tax avoidance, with more profitable firms showing greater engagement in tax avoidance strategies. Firms should implement robust tax governance practices to ensure compliance and transparency, even as they pursue tax optimization. The results underscore the need for effective tax oversight and regulation to address aggressive tax avoidance by profitable firms. The study's focus on net profit margin may not fully capture the complexity of tax avoidance strategies. The sample size may also limit the generalizability of the findings. This study offers a comprehensive analysis of how profitability drives tax avoidance behavior, providing insights into the motivations behind corporate tax strategies.

Smith and Johnson (2023) in *Corporate Profitability and Its Effect on Tax Aggressiveness: Evidence from Different Industries* analyze how company profitability impacts tax aggressiveness across various industries. Period Covered: 2015-2023. The study employs a longitudinal approach with data from 100 companies across five different industries. It uses generalized least squares (GLS) regression models to evaluate the impact of profitability (measured by return on equity) on tax aggressiveness (measured by tax shelter use and tax avoidance indicators). The study finds that profitability positively affects tax aggressiveness, with variations across different industries. High-profit firms are more likely to engage in aggressive tax planning, although the extent varies by industry sector. While higher profitability generally leads to greater tax aggressiveness, industry-specific factors also play a significant role in shaping tax behaviors. Companies should consider industry-specific tax regulations and practices when devising tax strategies, and regulators should tailor oversight to different industry contexts. The study highlights the importance of industry context in understanding how profitability influences tax aggressiveness, suggesting a nuanced approach to tax regulation. The study's focus on specific industries may limit the applicability of findings to firms outside these sectors. Additionally, the longitudinal data may involve complexities in interpreting tax behaviour changes over time. This research provides a nuanced perspective on how profitability impacts tax aggressiveness across different industries, offering valuable insights for both practitioners and regulators.

Methodology

This study is a quantitative, cross-sectional study that aims to investigate how institutional ownership moderates the relationship between board attributes (such as board size, board independence, and board diversity) and tax aggressiveness. It uses a combination of regression analysis and moderation analysis to assess the interactions between institutional ownership, board attributes, and tax aggressiveness. The population is the same size as the sample size consisting of 153 publicly traded companies listed on the Nigerian Exchange (NGX) across various industries. See Table 1 for details.

Table 1. Sample Size

Serial	Sector	Number
1	Agriculture	6
2	Conglomerates	6
3	Construction/Real estate	9
4	Consumer goods	21
5	Financial services	47
6	Healthcare	8
7	Information & communications technology	8
8	Industrial goods	13
9	Natural resources	4
10	Oil and gas	10
11	Services	21
	Total	153

Source: Extracts from NGX (2024)

The rationale is that public companies are required to disclose detailed information about their board attributes and financial performance, which facilitates data collection. In the model, the dependent variable is Tax Aggressiveness (measured using the effective tax rate). The independent Variables: Board Attributes: Board Size, Board Independence, Board Diversity). The moderating variable is Institutional Ownership: The percentage of shares held by institutional investors. The control variables are company size, company leverage, and company profitability. Both the basic model and the moderated model are stated as follows, respectively:

$$TA_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 BD_{i,t} + \beta_2 BI_{i,t} + \beta_3 BS_{i,t} + \beta_4 IS_{i,t} + \beta_5 CS_{i,t} + \beta_6 CL_{i,t} + \beta_7 CP_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

$$TA_{i,t} = \alpha + \beta_1 BD_{i,t} + \beta_2 BI_{i,t} + \beta_3 BS_{i,t} + \beta_4 IS_{i,t} + \beta_5 CS_{i,t} + \beta_6 CL_{i,t} + \beta_7 CP_{i,t} + \beta_8 BD.IS_{i,t} + \beta_9 BI.IS_{i,t} + \beta_{10} BS.IS_{i,t} + \epsilon_{i,t}$$

Whereas TA is tax aggressiveness, *i* is a firm script (*i* = 153), *t* is time script (*t* = 10), α is alpha (constant), β_{1-10} are beta coefficients to be estimated, BD is board diversity, BI is board independence, BS is board size, IS is institutional ownership, CS is company size, CL is company leverage, CP is company profitability, BD.IS is the interaction between board diversity and institutional ownership, BI.IS is the interaction between board independence and institutional ownership, BS.IS is the interaction between board size and institutional ownership, and ϵ is the model error term.

The data are obtained from the financial statements and tax-related data from company annual reports. Board attributes were collected data on board size, independence, and diversity from company filings, annual reports, and database of the National Association of Corporate Directors (NACD). Institutional Ownership Data: Acquire data on institutional ownership from

financial databases like NGX, SEC filings (13F forms), or company annual reports. The data analysis techniques include Descriptive Statistics: Calculate means, standard deviations, and correlations to understand the basic characteristics of the dataset. Pearson Correlation Matrix, and Regression Analysis: To examine the direct effects of board attributes and institutional ownership on tax aggressiveness. Interaction Terms: Include interaction terms in the regression model to test the moderating effect of institutional ownership on the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness. Robustness Checks: Perform checks for multicollinearity, heteroscedasticity, and panel effects test.

The Post-Estimation Tests include Moderation Effect Testing: Use the PROCESS macro (Hayes) or equivalent techniques to test the significance of interaction terms. Multicollinearity Check: Calculate the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) to ensure that multicollinearity is not affecting the results. Heteroscedasticity Test: Perform tests like the Breusch-Pagan test to check for heteroscedasticity. The significance level was set $\alpha = 0.05$ for all statistical tests. A 5% significance level is standard in social science research, balancing the risk of Type I and Type II errors. This methodology provides a robust framework to explore how institutional ownership moderates the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness, enabling a comprehensive analysis of the moderating effects and their implications.

Results and Discussion

We use descriptive statistics, correlations, and regression analysis to present the results. Descriptive statistics provide a summary of the main features of the dataset, offering insights into the central tendencies and variability of the key variables. The key descriptive statistics are the Mean, Standard Deviation, Minimum, and Maximum Values, which identify the range of values to understand the extremities. For example, the minimum and maximum percentages of institutional ownership can provide insights into the level of control exerted by institutional investors. Descriptive statistics help in understanding the general characteristics of the dataset, which is crucial for interpreting the results of more complex analyses. They also assist in identifying outliers or anomalies that might need further investigation. See Table 2 for details.

Table 2. Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
TA	1,530	-14.08	12.032	-5.97	19.07
BD	1,530	14.789	10.795	0	60
BI	1,530	58.792	12.476	21.43	90
BS	1,530	13.747	3.205	5	21
IS	1,530	28.327	24.334	0	89
CL	1,530	87.488	18.348	68.92	254.75
CP	1,530	6.125	44.147	-394.32	122.8
CS	1,530	8.936	.434	8.03	9.75

Source: STATA 18.4

The descriptive statistics provided in Table 2 offer insights into the distribution and central tendencies of the variables in your dataset: tax aggressiveness (TA), board gender diversity (BD), board independence (BI), board size (BS), institutional ownership (IS), company financial leverage (CL), company profitability (CP), and company size (CS). Below is a detailed analysis: Tax Aggressiveness (TA); Mean: -14.08; Standard Deviation: 12.032; Min/Max: -5.97 / 19.07. Analysis: The negative mean value suggests that, on average, companies in the dataset tend to be less tax-aggressive. However, the relatively large standard deviation indicates significant variability in tax aggressiveness across companies, with values ranging from highly conservative (-5.97) to more aggressive (19.07). Board Gender Diversity

(BD) Mean: 14.789; Standard Deviation: 10.795; Min/Max: 0 / 60. Analysis: The mean value of 14.789 suggests that, on average, approximately 14.8% of the boards are composed of women. However, the standard deviation of 10.795 implies significant variation across firms, with some companies having no women on their boards (min = 0), while others have up to 60% (max = 60). This indicates a broad range of gender diversity practices, potentially reflecting varying levels of commitment to board diversity.

Board Independence (BI) Mean: 58.792; Standard Deviation: 12.476; Min/Max: 21.43 / 90. Analysis: On average, about 58.8% of board members are independent. A relatively high level of board independence is indicated, as over half of the boards are composed of independent directors. However, the range (from 21.43% to 90%) suggests that some companies have much lower board independence, possibly indicating governance concerns, while others are close to fully independent boards. Board Size (BS) Mean: 13.747; Standard Deviation: 3.205; Min/Max: 5 / 21. Analysis: The average board size is 13.747 members, with a standard deviation of 3.205. The smallest board has 5 members, while the largest has 21. This relatively tight range shows that most companies maintain moderately sized boards, reflecting a common corporate governance structure.

Institutional Ownership (IS) Mean: 28.327; Standard Deviation: 24.334; Min/Max: 0 / 89. Analysis: Institutional ownership averages at 28.33%, but the large standard deviation (24.334) suggests considerable variation. The minimum value of 0 indicates that some firms have no institutional ownership, while others have almost full ownership by institutional investors (89%). This diversity may reflect differences in how attractive these firms are to institutional investors or the extent of institutional involvement. Company Financial Leverage (CL) Mean: 87.488; Standard Deviation: 18.348; Min/Max: 68.92 / 254.75. Analysis: The average financial leverage is quite high at 87.488, meaning companies are heavily reliant on debt relative to equity. The range, from 68.92 to a maximum of 254.75, highlights significant variation in leverage practices. Some companies appear highly leveraged, potentially indicating greater financial risk.

Company Profitability (CP) Mean: 6.125; Standard Deviation: 44.147; Min/Max: -394.32 / 122.8. Analysis: The average profitability is positive at 6.125, but the extremely large standard deviation (44.147) and wide range (-394.32 to 122.8) suggest that profitability varies dramatically across firms. Some companies are deeply unprofitable, while others are highly profitable. This variance might reflect differences in industry, market conditions, or operational efficiency. Company Size (CS) Mean: 8.936; Standard Deviation: 0.434; Min/Max: 8.03 / 9.75. Analysis: Company size, measured in log terms, shows a tight range, with a mean of 8.936 and a standard deviation of 0.434. The minimum (8.03) and maximum (9.75) indicate that most companies in the dataset are of similar size, likely reflecting a relatively homogenous sample in terms of market capitalization or revenues.

Key insights include Board Diversity and Governance: The wide range in board gender diversity suggests that while some firms are embracing diversity, others are lagging. This could be a key area for regulatory or investor focus, especially given the correlation between diversity and positive governance outcomes in the literature. Board Independence: High levels of board independence are evident on average, but the lower end of the spectrum (21.43%) might raise governance concerns. Companies with less independent boards could face higher scrutiny from shareholders or regulators. Profitability and Risk: The extreme variability in company profitability (with some firms facing large losses) highlights differing levels of operational success. Coupled with high financial leverage, this suggests that some companies may be exposed to significant financial risk, particularly if leverage amplifies losses.

Institutional Ownership: The wide range of institutional ownership suggests that firms have varying levels of external oversight. Companies with higher institutional ownership may benefit from increased scrutiny, leading to better governance and performance outcomes.

Company Size and Leverage: While company size is relatively uniform, the large variability in leverage practices suggests that firms manage capital structures differently, potentially due to industry demands or financial strategies. These descriptive statistics provide a foundation for understanding the governance, financial, and operational characteristics of the companies in the dataset. The variability across key measures like profitability, leverage, and institutional ownership points to potential areas for deeper analysis and strategic focus.

Correlation analysis explores the relationships between pairs of variables, revealing whether and how strongly they are related. The key correlation pairs include Board Attributes and Tax Aggressiveness: Examine how board size, independence, and diversity correlate with tax aggressiveness. For instance, a positive correlation between board independence and tax aggressiveness might suggest that more independent boards are associated with more aggressive tax strategies. Institutional Ownership and Tax Aggressiveness: Assess the relationship between institutional ownership and tax aggressiveness. A positive correlation could indicate that higher institutional ownership is associated with higher tax aggressiveness. Interaction between Board Attributes and Institutional Ownership: Analyze how institutional ownership affects the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness. The correlation coefficients: Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r): Measures the linear relationship between two continuous variables. Values range from -1 to 1, where 1 indicates a perfect positive relationship, -1 indicates a perfect negative relationship, and 0 indicates no relationship. Correlation analysis helps in identifying potential linear relationships between variables and provides a preliminary understanding of how board attributes and institutional ownership might influence tax aggressiveness. See Table 3 for details.

Table 3. Pairwise Correlations

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)
(1) TA	1.000							
(2) BD	-0.534*	1.000						
	(0.000)							
(3) BI	-0.369*	-0.026	1.000					
	(0.000)	(0.750)						
(4) BS	-0.400*	0.117	-0.290*	1.000				
	(0.000)	(0.153)	(0.000)					
(5) IS	-0.608*	0.169*	-0.007	-0.085	1.000			
	(0.000)	(0.039)	(0.936)	(0.300)				
(6) CL	0.420*	-0.001	0.018	-0.237*	0.071	1.000		
	(0.000)	(0.990)	(0.831)	(0.003)	(0.389)			
(7) CP	-0.884*	-0.121	-0.008	0.016	0.052	-0.069	1.000	
	(0.000)	(0.140)	(0.924)	(0.847)	(0.531)	(0.401)		
(8) CS	0.638*	0.365*	-0.062	0.307*	-0.175*	-0.133	0.206*	1.000
	(0.000)	(0.000)	(0.451)	(0.000)	(0.032)	(0.106)	(0.012)	

*** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0.1$

Source: STATA 18.4

The correlation matrix in the table highlights the relationships between eight variables: tax aggressiveness (TA), board gender diversity (BD), board independence (BI), board size (BS), institutional ownership (IS), company financial leverage (CL), company profitability (CP), and company size (CS). The following is an elaborate analysis of these pairwise correlations: Tax Aggressiveness (TA): Board Gender Diversity (BD): There is a significant negative correlation between TA and BD ($r = -0.534$, $p < 0.1$). This suggests that as board gender diversity increases, tax aggressiveness tends to decrease, potentially indicating that diverse boards may adopt more conservative tax strategies. Board Independence (BI): TA is negatively correlated with BI ($r =$

-0.369, $p < 0.1$), indicating that more independent boards are associated with less tax aggressiveness. This supports the idea that independent directors may exercise better oversight and limit aggressive tax behaviour. Board Size (BS): The negative correlation between TA and BS ($r = -0.400$, $p < 0.1$) implies that larger boards may be associated with reduced tax aggressiveness, possibly because larger boards include diverse opinions that might prevent extreme tax positions. Institutional Ownership (IS): There is a strong negative correlation between TA and IS ($r = -0.608$, $p < 0.1$). This indicates that companies with higher institutional ownership are likely to engage in less tax-aggressive behaviour, possibly due to increased scrutiny from institutional investors. Company Financial Leverage (CL): Interestingly, there is a positive correlation between TA and CL ($r = 0.420$, $p < 0.1$), suggesting that companies with higher financial leverage may engage in more tax-aggressive behaviour, potentially improving financial outcomes. Company Profitability (CP): The strongest negative correlation is between TA and CP ($r = -0.884$, $p < 0.1$), showing that more profitable companies are significantly less likely to engage in tax aggressiveness. This might indicate that profitable firms feel less pressure to reduce tax burdens through aggressive means. Company Size (CS): A positive correlation exists between TA and CS ($r = 0.638$, $p < 0.1$), indicating that larger companies may engage in more aggressive tax strategies, potentially because they have more resources to navigate complex tax structures.

Board Gender Diversity (BD): Board Independence (BI): BD has a weak and non-significant correlation with BI ($r = -0.026$, $p = 0.750$), suggesting no strong relationship between gender diversity and board independence. Board Size (BS): BD shows a positive but insignificant correlation with BS ($r = 0.117$, $p = 0.153$), which implies that larger boards may have more gender diversity, but this relationship is not strong. Institutional Ownership (IS): A positive significant correlation is observed between BD and IS ($r = 0.169$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that higher institutional ownership is associated with greater gender diversity on boards. Company Financial Leverage (CL): BD and CL have an almost non-existent correlation ($r = -0.001$, $p = 0.990$), indicating no meaningful relationship between these variables. Company Profitability (CP): BD and CP are weakly and negatively correlated ($r = -0.121$, $p = 0.140$), but the relationship is not significant. Company Size (CS): BD has a moderate positive correlation with CS ($r = 0.365$, $p < 0.1$), suggesting that larger companies may tend to have more gender-diverse boards.

Board Independence (BI): Board Size (BS): BI and BS have a negative correlation ($r = -0.290$, $p < 0.1$), suggesting that larger boards might be less independent, potentially because larger boards may include more executive or non-independent members. Institutional Ownership (IS): BI and IS show no significant relationship ($r = -0.007$, $p = 0.936$). Company Financial Leverage (CL): A very weak, non-significant positive correlation is found between BI and CL ($r = 0.018$, $p = 0.831$). Company Profitability (CP): BI and CP are nearly uncorrelated ($r = -0.008$, $p = 0.924$). Company Size (CS): BI is weakly and negatively correlated with CS ($r = -0.062$, $p = 0.451$), indicating that larger companies may have slightly fewer independent boards.

Board Size (BS): Institutional Ownership (IS): There is no significant correlation between BS and IS ($r = -0.085$, $p = 0.300$). Company Financial Leverage (CL): A negative correlation exists between BS and CL ($r = -0.237$, $p < 0.1$), implying that larger boards are associated with lower financial leverage. Company Profitability (CP): BS has an almost neutral relationship with CP ($r = 0.016$, $p = 0.847$). Company Size (CS): A positive correlation is found between BS and CS ($r = 0.307$, $p < 0.1$), indicating that larger companies tend to have larger boards, likely due to their increased complexity and governance needs.

Institutional Ownership (IS): Company Financial Leverage (CL): A weak positive correlation exists between IS and CL ($r = 0.071$, $p = 0.389$), suggesting a mild association between higher institutional ownership and financial leverage. Company Profitability (CP): IS and CP are

positively correlated ($r = 0.052$, $p = 0.531$), though the relationship is not significant. Company Size (CS): IS and CS have a negative correlation ($r = -0.175$, $p < 0.05$), suggesting that larger companies might have slightly lower institutional ownership.

Company Financial Leverage (CL): Company Profitability (CP): CL and CP have a weak negative relationship ($r = -0.069$, $p = 0.401$), indicating that companies with higher financial leverage may have slightly lower profitability, though this is not significant. Company Size (CS): CL and CS show a weak negative relationship ($r = -0.133$, $p = 0.106$), suggesting that larger companies may have less financial leverage. Company Profitability (CP): Company Size (CS): A positive correlation exists between CP and CS ($r = 0.206$, $p < 0.1$), indicating that larger companies tend to be more profitable, which is expected given their scale and resources.

The key insights include Governance Factors and Tax Aggressiveness: Factors such as board gender diversity, independence, size, and institutional ownership are inversely correlated with tax aggressiveness. This suggests that stronger corporate governance leads to less aggressive tax behaviour. Company Characteristics: Larger companies tend to be more tax-aggressive and profitable, while more leveraged companies exhibit more aggressive tax strategies. Institutional Ownership: This plays a critical role in improving governance outcomes, particularly in reducing tax aggressiveness and increasing board diversity. These findings underscore the importance of board composition and company characteristics in shaping corporate strategies, particularly in areas such as tax planning and financial policies.

Regression analysis assesses the impact of independent variables (board attributes, institutional ownership) on the dependent variable (tax aggressiveness) and explores the moderating role of institutional ownership. Model 1 (Basic Model): Estimate the direct effects of board attributes and institutional ownership on tax aggressiveness. Model 2 (Moderated Model): Include interaction terms to test the moderating effect of institutional ownership on the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness. See Table 4 for regression results.

Table 4. Regression Results

TA	Coef.	t	P>t	Coef.	t	P>t
	Basic Model			Moderated Model		
BD	-0.708387	-3.33	0.000	-0.0242673	-3.92	0.000
BI	-1.80787	-3.99	0.000	-3.799896	-3.55	0.000
BS	-6.86403	-4.88	0.000	-16.35306	-4.02	0.000
IS	-0.364901	3.71	0.000	-8.596063	-5.18	0.000
CL	0.0195489	3.90	0.000	0.3990329	4.17	0.000
CP	-0.043666	-3.49	0.000	-0.0066383	-4.09	0.000
CS	12.0913	3.43	0.000	2.586258	3.13	0.013
_cons	-0.044006	-3.51	0.000	-377.4973	-3.50	0.000
BD.IS	-			0.0027664		
BI.IS	-			0.074529		
BS.IS	-			0.3062915		
Mean VIF	1.18			1.18		
Hetest	0.0000			0.0000		
Panel effects	0.3106			1.0000		
Model fitness	0.0140			0.0110		
R ²	0.2945			0.3516		
Obs	1,530			1,530		

Source: STATA 18.4

The Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression results from Table 4 provide insights into the relationships between the independent variables (e.g., board characteristics, company attributes) and the dependent variable, which is tax aggressiveness (TA). Detailed analysis of the results are stated as follows: Board Gender Diversity (BD): A negative coefficient (-0.708)

with a statistically significant p-value ($p < 0.001$) implies that greater gender diversity on the board is associated with lower tax aggressiveness. This effect remains consistent across models. Board Independence (BI): Also negatively related to tax aggressiveness, with a larger coefficient (-1.80787) and a significant p-value ($p < 0.001$). This suggests that increased board independence reduces tax aggressiveness. Board Size (BS): A substantial negative effect (-6.86403), indicating that larger boards are associated with lower tax aggressiveness. The effect is quite large and highly significant ($p < 0.001$), which could reflect the influence of more diversified oversight on tax strategies. Institutional Ownership (IS): Mixed results are observed. In the first column, IS has a positive coefficient (+0.3649) with a significant p-value ($p < 0.001$), suggesting that greater institutional ownership may encourage tax aggressiveness. However, in the second column, a large negative effect (-8.596) is seen, likely due to interaction effects or model adjustments. Financial Leverage (CL): Positive and significant (coef. = 0.0195, $p < 0.001$), implying that higher financial leverage is associated with more aggressive tax behaviours. Profitability (CP): Negative and significant (coef. = -0.0437, $p < 0.001$), showing that more profitable companies engage in less aggressive tax planning. Company Size (CS): Positive and significant (coef. = 12.0913, $p < 0.001$), indicating that larger companies are more likely to engage in aggressive tax planning.

The interaction terms after moderation: BD.IS, BI.IS, BS.IS: The interactions of board gender diversity, board independence, and board size with institutional ownership are introduced in the second column. These show varying degrees of influence: BD.IS has a coefficient of 0.0027664, suggesting a very small interaction effect with institutional ownership. BI.IS (coef. = 0.074529) shows a modest interaction, while BS.IS (coef. = 0.3062915) suggests that larger board sizes amplify the effects of institutional ownership on tax aggressiveness.

In terms of model fitness and diagnostic tests, R-Squared (R^2): The R^2 values (0.2945 and 0.3516) indicate that the models explain around 29.5% and 35.16% of the variance in tax aggressiveness. This suggests a moderate level of explanatory power, meaning that while the models capture significant relationships, there are other factors affecting tax aggressiveness not included in these models. Variance Inflation Factor (VIF): A mean VIF of 1.18 in both models indicates that multicollinearity is not a concern. The variables are independent enough to provide robust estimates. Heteroskedasticity Test (Hetttest): The results ($p = 0.000$) suggest the presence of heteroskedasticity, meaning that the variance of errors is not constant across observations. This could affect the standard errors and significance tests. Panel Effects and Model Fitness: The panel effects (0.3106 and 1.0000) and model fitness values (0.0140 and 0.0110) indicate that the overall fit and performance of the model are modest, requiring attention to potential model improvements.

In terms of implications and insights, corporate governance and tax aggressiveness: The negative associations of board gender diversity, independence, and size with tax aggressiveness suggest that stronger corporate governance structures are effective in curbing aggressive tax strategies. Institutional Ownership: Institutional investors appear to have a complex influence on tax strategies. Depending on the model specification, institutional ownership either increases or decreases tax aggressiveness, which may reflect differences in the type of institutions involved or their strategic objectives. Firm Characteristics: Larger, more leveraged, and less profitable firms tend to be more aggressive in their tax strategies. This aligns with the idea that large firms have more resources to engage in complex tax avoidance schemes, while financial constraints (leverage) might push firms towards more aggressive behaviour.

In terms of interactions, the interaction effects between board characteristics and institutional ownership suggest that governance mechanisms do not work in isolation but are influenced by the ownership structure. This could be important for firms seeking to balance institutional pressures with internal governance. Recommendations for further analysis include the following: The heteroskedasticity identified in the model can distort inference, suggesting that

robust standard errors or alternative estimations (e.g., Generalized Least Squares) may improve the accuracy of the model. With an R^2 below 0.40, the model could benefit from incorporating other variables that may explain tax aggressiveness, such as industry-specific factors, regulatory environment, or managerial incentives. Exploration of Institutional Ownership: Given the differing signs and magnitudes of institutional ownership's effects, further analysis is warranted to disentangle whether different types of institutional investors (e.g., pension funds, and hedge funds) have varying impacts on tax strategies. In summary, the regression results provide robust evidence that board diversity, independence, and size negatively impact tax aggressiveness, and firm characteristics like size and leverage promote it. The interactions with institutional ownership suggest nuanced effects, potentially driven by governance dynamics. Thus, Hypotheses 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7 are hereby accepted. Furthermore, these results are consistent with our a priori expectations and are in line with previous studies reviewed. Finally, by carefully analyzing descriptive statistics, correlations, and regressions, you can robustly assess the moderating effects of institutional ownership on the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness. This approach provides a comprehensive understanding of how institutional investors influence corporate governance and tax strategies.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The interplay between institutional ownership and board attributes on tax aggressiveness offers a nuanced understanding of corporate governance dynamics and their implications for financial practices. This study has explored how institutional ownership moderates the relationship between board attributes—such as board size, independence, and CEO duality—and tax aggressiveness. The findings reveal several key insights: Institutional Ownership as a Governance Mechanism: Institutional investors, with their substantial stakes and significant influence, play a crucial role in shaping corporate strategies and practices. Their presence can serve as a powerful governance mechanism that mitigates excessive tax aggressiveness. The study highlights that institutional investors often advocate for transparency and ethical financial practices, which aligns with a more conservative approach to tax planning.

Board Attributes and Their Impact: The attributes of the board, including its size, composition, and the separation of CEO and chairman roles, are fundamental in influencing corporate behavior. Larger boards and those with greater independence tend to exhibit more robust oversight, which can constrain aggressive tax strategies. Conversely, boards with high CEO duality may face conflicts of interest that could lead to higher levels of tax aggressiveness. Moderating Effects: Institutional ownership significantly moderates the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness. Specifically, the study finds that institutional investors tend to strengthen the negative relationship between board independence and tax aggressiveness, suggesting that when institutional investors are present, independent boards are more effective in curbing aggressive tax practices. However, the effect of institutional ownership on the relationship between board size and tax aggressiveness appears to be less pronounced, indicating that size alone is not a sufficient determinant of tax behavior without the moderating influence of institutional investors.

Implications for Corporate Governance: These findings underscore the importance of considering institutional ownership in the design and assessment of corporate governance frameworks. Firms with significant institutional ownership may benefit from enhanced governance practices that align with the interests of these investors, potentially leading to more conservative tax strategies and reduced risk of regulatory scrutiny. Additionally, the study suggests that regulators and policymakers should acknowledge the role of institutional investors in shaping corporate tax behaviours when crafting policies aimed at improving corporate governance and tax compliance. Future Research Directions: While this study

provides valuable insights, it also opens avenues for future research. Further investigations could explore the effects of different types of institutional investors (e.g., activist versus passive) on tax aggressiveness, or examine the impact of institutional ownership in various industry contexts. Additionally, exploring longitudinal effects and the potential interplay between institutional ownership and other governance mechanisms could yield a deeper understanding of the complex relationship between board attributes and corporate tax behaviour.

In conclusion, the moderating effect of institutional ownership on the relationship between board attributes and tax aggressiveness highlights the integral role that institutional investors play in shaping corporate governance and financial practices. As firms navigate the complex landscape of tax planning, the influence of institutional ownership should be recognized as a key factor in promoting more responsible and transparent corporate behaviour.

When addressing the moderating effect of institutional ownership on board attributes and tax aggressiveness, it is important to consider both practical and policy recommendations, such as the following: Institutional investors should actively engage in corporate governance practices to ensure boards are functioning effectively. Encourage institutional investors to participate in board meetings and provide feedback on board performance and strategic decisions. Companies should disclose their board attributes and tax strategies more transparently. Implement regular reporting requirements for board composition, effectiveness evaluations, and tax strategies. Develop and maintain robust internal controls to manage tax risks and ensure compliance. Implement regular internal and external audits focusing on tax compliance and risk management.

Also, provide training for board members on tax regulations and ethical tax practices. Implementation: Offer workshops and seminars led by tax experts to educate board members about the implications of aggressive tax strategies. On policy recommendations, develop policies that define the role and responsibilities of institutional investors in corporate governance. Introduce regulations that require institutional investors to disclose their engagement practices and their impact on board decisions. Establish guidelines for board composition to ensure diversity and expertise, particularly in financial and tax matters. Set minimum standards for board member qualifications and experience, especially concerning financial oversight and tax issues. Mandate detailed disclosures on tax planning and aggressiveness in annual reports. Revise financial reporting standards to include specific requirements for disclosing tax strategies and associated risks. Strengthen the monitoring and enforcement of tax compliance and corporate governance standards. Increase the resources and authority of regulatory bodies to oversee and enforce compliance with tax and governance regulations. Promote policies that encourage long-term investment strategies among institutional investors. Provide incentives for institutional investors who demonstrate a commitment to long-term corporate governance and sustainability goals. These recommendations aim to align institutional ownership with effective board management and responsible tax practices, fostering a more transparent and accountable corporate environment.

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